

ESSENTIAL STAGES FOR ENHANCING LEXICAL SKILLS IN ENGLISH COURSES AT NON-PHILOLOGICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS THROUGH CASE STUDIES

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Abstract: *General conclusions are given about the use of modern teaching methods, their positive impact on the professional development of students, as well as the importance of modern technologies in teaching English today. This article presents a methodology for teaching English for specific purposes using case-study technology. Relevant examples from the specialized literature on this method are given, and special attention is paid to the positive impact of problem-based learning technology on the educational process. Especially in the areas of energy education, when training sessions are organized using problem-based learning technology, we see the development of students' lexical base and improvement of language skills. The importance of case-study technology in teaching English in non-philological institutions and the advantages of this approach in language learning by students discussed.*

Keywords: *methodology, foreign language, lexical competence, case studies, material design, education, English for Specific Purposes (ESP), non-philological directions, development, technology, audience.*

ОСНОВНЫЕ ЭТАПЫ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИХ НАВЫКОВ В КУРСАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В НЕФИЛОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ВУЗАХ ЧЕРЕЗ КЕЙС-СТАДИ

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Аннотация: *В данной статье приведены общие выводы об использовании современных методов обучения, их положительном влиянии на профессиональное развитие студентов, а также о значении современных технологий в преподавании английского языка сегодня. Также представлена методика обучения английскому языку для специальных целей с использованием технологии кейс-стади, приводятся соответствующие примеры из специальной литературы по этому методу, особое внимание уделяется положительному влиянию технологии проблемного обучения на учебный процесс. Обсуждается важность технологии кейс-стади в обучении английскому языку в нефилологических образовательных учреждениях и преимущества такого подхода*

в изучении языка студентами. Использование технологии проблемного обучения в процессе преподавания студентам, обучающимся по направлениям энергетики, способствует развитию лексической базы студентов и улучшению языковых навыков.

Ключевые слова: методология, иностранный язык, лексическая компетенция, кейс-стади, материальный дизайн, образование, английский язык для специальных целей, нефилологические направления, развитие, технология, аудитория

NOFILOLOGIK OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA INGLIZ TILI KURSLARIDA LEKSIK KO'NIKMALARNI O'RGANISHNING MUHIM BOSQICHLARI

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Annotatsiya: Zamonaviy o'qitish metodlaridan foydalanish, ularning talabalarning kasbiy rivojlanishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi va bugungi kundagi ingliz tilini o'qitishda zamonaviy texnologiyalarning ahamiyati haqida umumiy xulosalar berib o'tilgan. Ushbu maqolada case-study texnologiyasidan foydalangan holda maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tilini o'qitish metodikasi keltirilgan. Bu metodga oid maxsus adabiyotlardan tegishli misollar keltirilgan bo'lib, muammoli o'qitish texnologiyasining ta'lim jarayoniga ijobiy ta'siriga alohida urg'u berilgan. Ayniqsa, energetika ta'lim yo'nalishlarida muammoli o'qitish texnologiyasidan foydalanib o'quv mashg'ulotlari tashkil etilganda, talabalarda leksik bazaning rivojlanganligini, til ko'nikmalarining yaxshilanganini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Nofilologik ta'lim muassasalarida ingliz tilini o'qitishda case-study texnologiyasining ahamiyati va o'quvchilar tomonidan til o'rganishda ushbu yondashuvning afzalliklari haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: metodologiya, chet tili, leksik kompetentlik, chorak tadqiqotlari, materiallarni loyihalash, ta'lim, muayyan maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili (ESP), filologik bo'lmagan yo'nalishlar, rivojlanish, texnologiya, auditoriya.

INTRODUCTION

Today English is becoming crucial language to learn. The number of people learning this language is increasing day by day, and their goals for learning this language are also different. Someone is learning English in order to enter higher education institutions, and the others are learning it in order to take advantage of the additional opportunities provided by our state at their workplaces.

Our ability to understand and accept all the changes in science, news in the field of medicine, and new terms entering technology depends on how well we know the English language.

For this reason, teaching various foreign languages, especially English, using effective methods and technologies in non-philological fields is a requirement of

today. Otherwise, it is inevitable that we will face difficulties in preparing competitive personnel for the developed countries in the field of science.

Field-oriented English language teaching in non-philological educational institutions is becoming an important branch in the field of language teaching. In this regard, we can cite several examples of work being carried out in our country.

In the project carried out in 2016, in cooperation with the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic Scientific and Practical Innovation Center, with the participation of several higher educational institutions operating in our country, curricula for non-philological fields, a materials development program was launched.

A total of 31 higher educational institutions participated in this pilot project and agreed to implement the necessary plans. Within the framework of this project, a science program that systematizes English language teaching for special purposes has been developed. Today, on the basis of this program, a number of non-philological higher education institutions of Uzbekistan have effectively started teaching English in the field.

The unique feature of this program is that practical training is organized not from one book or source, but from any source based on the needs analysis of students, and the possibility of wide use of modern pedagogical, educational and information technologies.

According to methodical literature, in order to choose the content of teaching foreign languages, it is necessary to fulfill the following basic requirements:

- To be feasible, to respond to the interests and needs of modern students, to introduce them to the cultural heritage of the motherland and foreign countries, to be authentic, to form a holistic view of the world in the minds of students, to help prepare them for society
- Focusing on the personal experience of students, their feelings and emotions, teaching comparison and helping to develop critical thinking; teaching to express one's point of view, in general, comprehensive development of the individual, helping to educate as a patriot of one's country and a citizen of the world, helping to show tolerance towards other mentality and culture
- Creating a realistic environment for students to implement a differentiated and individualized approach, considering their needs, abilities and capabilities
- Stimulating the subjective state of students in learning, observing the communication process, independent thinking and giving conclusions, teaching them to participate in conversations, as well as directing them to independently search for information (including using Internet resources)

➤ Continual self-education and development (self-monitoring, self-management, evaluation), fostering the development of critical thinking skills, as well as student self-determination and promoting self-awareness⁴

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We can see that several components should be considered when choosing the content of foreign language education. Therefore, every teacher should prepare any material for the student based on the above requirements. In this, it is important to pay attention to the interests and needs of the student, to consider his feelings and desires.

Creating resources that encourage students to think critically help self-education, and independently search for information from various resources is one of the most urgent issues today.

Using the effectiveness of case technology in foreign language teaching not only in the field of energy, which we are conducting research on, increases the quality of learning, but also in other different directions. Below, we can see that problem-based learning technology is effectively used in the areas of medicine and agriculture.

It was mentioned that when using this technology, students have not only strengthened their knowledge of the field, but also acquired a number of professional skills that will help them become mature specialists in their professions in the future.

For example, in the science syllabus "ESP Syllabus Agrarian Studies" created within the framework of this program, various problematic situations are created in tasks related to the organization of independent work, and on the basis of them, tasks directed to free thinking of students in a mutually active form are given.

Assessment

a) possible authentic tasks: (including people, context and purpose)

Scenario: You are a farmer. You have problem with irrigation issues on your farm. The National Irrigation Department is postponing watering your fields. Prepare a complaint form to the Department. Introduce yourself, present your problem, ask them to look your enquiry and find out a solution to it.

b) Possible pedagogical tasks:

Scenario: Listening for specific information. Students watch the video about the green houses near the Fucusima Nuclear station in Japan and write the cause/effect analysis.

Answers should be given to the following questions:

- What is the problem?

⁴ Миролюбова, А. А. Методика обучения иностранным языкам: традиции и современность / Под ред.— Обнинск: Титул, 2010. — 464 с

- How is it influenced the result?
- What should be done to avoid the problem?
- What reforms should be done?
- Who should be involved to the process of solving the problem?⁵

The fact that the task given above is aimed at creating a problem situation and using it to encourage the student to think in English shows the elements of the case. Effective use of similar techniques can be effective in teaching English for special purposes. Several types of case technologies can be widely used in English classes for technical profile courses. In particular, the development of the lexical competence of energy students by means of cases was the main goal of our research. It would be appropriate to create different packages of cases in each direction depending on the level of knowledge of students.

In this regard, it is appropriate to look at the works of several scientists, including Alimova. According to F. Zakirovna's article entitled "Innovative technologies in the training of medical personnel", among the innovative technologies that activate the educational process, it is possible to distinguish the method of situational analysis, which includes the analysis of a specific situation.

Today, the following methods are used more often in situational analysis: situational analysis (situational issues, situational exercises) method, case method, game design, role-playing method. CBL (Case Based Learning) technologies are widely used in cynic departments.

Technology develops a competent approach to diagnosis and treatment in the future doctor. At the case stage, specific clinical situations, problem solving are seen, identification of signs and their integration into clinical syndromes, and identification of the leading syndrome are studied. For such technology, it is necessary to develop clinical situations, for example, the respiratory system, the cardiovascular system, the nervous system, the digestive system, etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The advantages of the case study method over the traditional method are: increased attendance, formation of a positive attitude to the teaching process, strengthening of long-term memory, motivation to study, improvement of problem solving skills. The meaning of the method is that the student is not given ready-made knowledge; he must develop ways to solve the problem himself. In problem-based teaching technology, the teacher acts as a leader. Asks questions, supports the discussion, directs students to the goal when necessary, that is, acts as a dispatcher.⁶

⁵ Kholiyorov B., Khodjalepesova, I., Dawletnazarova S., Normatova, G. ESP syllabus for agrarian studies. Karshi. 2020. P-12-13.

⁶ Alimova Fotima Zakirovna. Innovative technologies in training of medical staff. "Science and Education" Scientific Journal. Volume 1 Issue 3

In the process of using this method, the teacher gives medical students a problem situation with a specific solution and asks them short questions about the same situation, which the student can understand, or presents a set of several academic tasks in written form. Based on the given instruction, students solve the problem independently and give all possible solutions with minimal teacher intervention. In developing the lexical competence of the medical requirements of the case stages, they begin to acquire new vocabulary and various skills in working with medical terms. In the requirements of this direction, not only professional skills are formed, but also the ability to communicate in the studied language, as well as writing skills in cases that provides a written solution.

Through this method, the assignment to the requirements is not presented in the form of ready-made material, but they themselves form the necessary knowledge and skills by collecting materials from various literatures, participating in discussions, and statistical analysis of various articles and scientific works. By applying the method of problem-based teaching to the educational process, it guarantees the development of teamwork and research skills in students, as well as the improvement of health care efficiency and, most importantly, the professional literacy of medical workers.

We believe that using this methodology in English classes in other non-philological areas will have a good effect. In order to develop lexical competence, it is appropriate to apply case assignments to the fields of the technical profile, in particular, to the students of the alternative energy field. The fact that there are many problem situations in this area gives the English teacher the opportunity to organize the materials effectively. For example, the problem of energy shortage can be presented as a task in the form of a case:

1. What is the problem?
2. What is the reason of that problem?
3. What are the possible solutions?
4. What is further procedure?

The development of lexical competence in non-philological areas through case technologies creates unlimited opportunities and conveniences for both the teacher and the student, but there are several conditions for using this technology, and the desired result can be obtained only if the teacher and the student can fulfill these conditions.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

This is obvious that there are some fundamental steps to apply a case study method into non-philological spheres. When teachers use this method in the classroom, effectiveness of the education quality will increase dramatically. Using different approaches such as learner-centered approach, may also supportive in

organizing practical English lessons in technical directions. Psychological surveys show that interactive lessons have shown more in percentage than in traditional sessions. It is important to combine both types of lessons in classroom to gain positive results. Using case study in teaching English language in technical directions is definitely very important and one of the urgent factors. There many scientific researches work to be conducted in this sphere.

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